

Synthesis and characterization of novel poly(*o*-anisidine)/graphene multifunctional nanocomposite

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Abstract : Poly(*o*-anisidine)/graphene (POA/G) nanocomposites were synthesized by chemical oxidative polymerization of *o*-anisidine with ammonium persulfate as an oxidant in the presence of graphene nanoparticles. The polymer nanocomposite was characterized by using FTIR, Raman and XRD techniques. The structure was characterized by XRD. FTIR spectrum confirms that the polymer nanocomposite is in conducting emeraldine salt phase. Raman spectrum reveals the presence of functional groups that account for the formation of nanocomposite.

Keywords : Poly(*o*-anisidine), graphene, nanocomposite, spectroscopy.

Introduction

In recent years, conducting polymers play a vital role in variety of advanced technologies as they possess conjugated π -bonds. Among these polymers, polyaniline (PANI) has emerged as a promising candidate with great potential due to its high electrical conductivity, good environmental stability, low cost, ease of synthesis and wide applications in sensors, electrical or optoelectronic devices, batteries, integrated circuits and field-effect transistors¹. However, due to its insolubility in common organic solvents and infusibility, the practical use of PANI has been limited. Intensive works have been made to improve the processability of PANI by using appropriate functionalized protonic acids or substituted PANI². In the later approach a suitable substituent is attached either in the phenyl ring or at the nitrogen atom of the repeat units. Among the substituted PANI derivatives, poly(*o*-anisidine) can be easily synthesized either chemically or electrochemically with higher processability and solubility as compared with PANI³.

The polymers of substituted derivatives of aniline exhibit slightly lower conductivity than that of unsubstituted PANI. To overcome this limitation, the combination of PANI with other nanomaterials, such as carbon might be good choice. As a new member of carbon nanomaterials, graphene, a two-dimensional and single layer sheet of sp^2

hybridized carbon atoms, has attracted a great deal of attention from both the experimental and theoretical scientific communities in the past several years due to its high surface area-to-volume ratio, excellent electrical conductivity, and remarkable mechanical stiffness which is very beneficial in designing electrochemical sensors⁴. In this work, we have discussed the synthesis of POA/G nanocomposite by chemical oxidative polymerization method, where graphene was obtained via a modified Hummers method. The present study shows the synthesis and characterization of POA/G nanocomposite by FTIR, Raman and XRD techniques.

Experimental

Materials :

The monomer *o*-anisidine (99%) was distilled under reduced pressure. Ammonium peroxydisulfate (98%), β -naphthalene sulphonic acid (70%), graphite (98%), H_2SO_4 (99%), $KMnO_4$ (99%), hydrazine were all of AR grade and used without further purification.

Experimental

Graphite Oxide (GO) was synthesized through oxidation of graphite with sulphuric acid and potassium permanganate (H_2SO_4 - $KMnO_4$). Reduction of GO to graphene was obtained via refluxing GO with hydrazine sulphate.

The POA/G nanocomposite was chemically synthesized by oxidative polymerization of *o*-anisidine using ammonium peroxydisulfate [(NH₄)₂S₂O₈] under controlled conditions. 1 M of *o*-anisidine and 1 M of β-naphthalene sulphonic acid (β-NSA) were added to de-ionized water with magnetic stirring at 5 °C for 30 min. Then 1 M of graphene was added into the mixture and stirred for 30 min. Ammonium peroxydisulfate (0.025 M) was also dissolved in 200 ml of 1 M β-NSA solution and precooled to 5 °C. Later, [(NH₄)₂S₂O₈] in 1 M β-NSA solution was added slowly in the *o*-anisidine solution, and the reaction was continued for 48 h. A dark green precipitate of the POA/G nanocomposite was obtained from the reaction vessel and it was filtered and washed using deionized water and acetone to remove any impurities. Further, this precipitate was heated at 60 °C⁵ in a temperature-controlled oven. The polymer nanocomposite was characterized by FTIR, Raman and XRD techniques.

Results and discussion

The FTIR spectrum of POA/G nanocomposite is shown in Fig. 1. The characteristic peaks of POA/G composite are observed at about 3722, 3210, 2887–3051, 1505–1571, 1700, 1454, 1303, 1212, 1123, 1027, 825, 750, 665 cm⁻¹. The peaks at 3210, 3051, 3722 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the N-H, C-H, O-H stretching vibration of POA ring. The band at 1454 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the C-H bending of -OCH₃ group⁶. The bands at 1571 and 1505 cm⁻¹ were attributed to the stretching mode of C=C for

Fig. 1. FTIR spectrum of POA/G nanocomposite.

the quinoid and benzenoid rings⁷. The bands at 1571 cm⁻¹ shows that the polymer is composed of amine unit. The band at 1303 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the emeraldine base structure⁷. The band at 1212 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the stretching of secondary aromatic amine³. The band at 1027 cm⁻¹ corresponds to C-O stretchings of methoxy group. The band at 1123 cm⁻¹ is due to SO₃⁻ group of the β-NSA indicates the efficient doping of POA⁸. The band at 825 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the 1,2,4-substitution in the benzenoid rings. The band at 665 cm⁻¹ is assigned to C-H out-of-plane ring deformation vibration. The band at 750 cm⁻¹ is out-of-plane C-H bending vibration³. It should be noted that, the peak due to C=O group within the POA/G has been down shifted to 1700 cm⁻¹, which is probably due to π-π interactions and hydrogen bonding between graphene and POA rings indicating that the carboxyl groups from graphene acted as efficient dopants in polymerization⁹.

Fig. 2 shows the Raman spectrum of the POA/G nanocomposite system. The Raman spectrum is a complementary technique to FTIR for the identification of vibrational modes at the surface of carbon based materials. The Raman bands at 1596 and 1331 cm⁻¹ are due to D peak and G peak respectively, indicating the lattice distortions of the graphene due to the presence of POA in the network⁶. The peak at 1517 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to the bipolaronic N-H bending vibration. C-N stretching vibration of the cation radical species can be seen at 1368

Fig. 2. Raman spectrum of POA/G nanocomposite.

cm^{-1} indicating an intermediate level of doping. The band at 1271 cm^{-1} corresponds to the stretching mode of C-N group connected to naphthalene ring unsubstituted with OH group¹⁰. The peak at 1134 cm^{-1} is C-H bending of quinoid ring. The peaks observed at 816, 722, 626 and 545 cm^{-1} can be assigned to bipolaronic quinoid ring deformations, bipolaronic C-C ring deformations, bipolaronic benzene ring deformation and bipolaronic amine deformation¹¹. The peak at 461 cm^{-1} is due to polaronic C-N-C torsion¹².

The structural analysis was carried out using X-ray diffractometer with $\text{CuK}\alpha_1$ ($\lambda = 0.15406\text{ nm}$). The XRD pattern of POA-G nanocomposite is shown in Fig. 3. For POA/G composite the sharp peak is centred at $2\theta = 25^\circ$ almost the same as that of pure POA, which was ascribed

Fig. 3. XRD pattern of POA/G nanocomposite.

to the diffraction peak of POA⁸. Additionally, the peak ascribed to graphene within these nanocomposites disappeared, illustrating the complete coating of POA between graphene layers.

Conclusion

In this work, a novel POA/G multifunctional nanocomposite was successfully synthesized by oxidative polymerization of *o*-anisidine in the presence of graphene nanoparticles. In FTIR spectra, the presence of vibration

band of the dopant ion and other characteristic bands confirmed that the POA/G nanocomposite is in conducting emeraldine salt phase. Raman spectrum reveals the formation of POA/G nanocomposite. XRD confirms the observed broadening of the overlap of polymer diffraction with graphene nanoparticles. This confirms that POA/G nanocomposite could be used as promising candidates for energy storage devices and sensors. Future work is focused on determining the electrochemical performances of the nanocomposite by cyclic voltammetry and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy techniques.

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References

1. H. Liu, X. Hu, J. Wang and R. Boughton, *Macromolecules*, 2002, **35**, 9414.
2. X. Lu, J. Zhang, D. Chao, J. Chen, W. Zhang and Y. Wei, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2006, **100**, 2356.
3. R. Jamal, T. Abdiriyim, Y. Ding and I. Nurulla, *J. Polym. Res.*, 2008, **15**, 75.
4. S. Stankovich, D. A. Dikin, G. H. B. Dommett, K. M. Kohlhaas, E. J. Zimney, E. A. Stach, R. D. Piner, S. T. Nguyen and R. S. Ruoff, *Nature*, 2006, **442**, 282.
5. J. Jiang, L. Hong and A. H. Liu, *Synth. Metals*, 2010, **160**, 333.
6. G. Humberto, K. R. Manoj, A. Farah, P. Villalba, S. Elias and Ashok Kumar, *J. Power Sources*, 2011, **196**, 4102.
7. M. Hasik, E. Wenda, C. Paluszkiwics, A. Bernasik and J. Camra, *Synth. Metals*, 2004, **143**, 341.
8. A. Givan, J. Grothe, A. Loewenschuss and C. J. Nielsen, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2002, **4**, 255.
9. D. Shaojun, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2012, **22**, 6300.
10. M. Vlassa, G. Borodi, A. Biris, G. Blanita and C. Sovestry, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 2011, **56**, 857.
11. L. Al-Mashat, K. Shin, K. Kalantar Zadeh, J. D. Plessis, S. H. Han, R. W. Kojima, R. B. Kaner, D. Li, G. Xing Long, Samuel, J. Ippolito and W. Wlodarski, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2010, **114**, 16168.
12. M. Couchet, G. Louarn, S. Quillard, J. P. Buisson and S. J. Lefran, *Raman. Spec.*, 2000, **31**, 1041.